

NAVIGATING CULTURAL WATERS: INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE AND EXPERIENCES OF SEA TEACHERS IN LABORATORY HIGH SCHOOL

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Navigating Cultural Waters: Intercultural Competence and Experiences of SEA Teachers in Laboratory High School

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Abstract

Student-teacher exchange programs push society and education towards internationalization, involving teachers from various countries to experience education in a foreign environment. Naturally, this challenges one's capacity to adapt to changes and cultural differences. Using a qualitative method, semi-structured focus group discussions positioned this phenomenological study to discover experiences shared by six Southeast Asian Teachers Project Pilot Batch 2 interns from Japan, Indonesia, and Thailand and determine the importance of intercultural competence in cross-cultural education, evaluated through thematic analysis. By socializing with local Filipino students and professionals, intercultural competence was determined as a crucial aspect when interacting with students from different cultural backgrounds. Despite struggles in their first teaching experience, such as communication, cultural adaptation, and technological differences, it was noted that English as a second-acquired language paved the way for efficient communication, thus understanding the international language's significance in a globalized world. Concepts of intercultural awareness and competence should be applied to international student-teacher exchange programs to make the overall process more accessible, making a lot more socially mobile for student-teacher experiences. The SEA Teacher Project offers opportunities for student-teachers to foster cross-cultural understanding. Global competence is only the beginning of gaining innovative perspectives on internationalizing education.

Keywords: *intercultural awareness, internationalization, education, cultural competence*

Introduction

With the amount of information and technology exchanged from one country to another, humanity's push toward globalization has led people into a more interdependent society. This push towards globalization has caused education systems of various countries to involve themselves more internationally (Krechetnikov & Mihina, 2019; Deardoff, 2011; Kim & Lee, 2019) while students are given opportunities to study abroad and participate in international internships and research programs (Strielkowski et al., 2021).

This study is grounded on (1) the Cultural Intelligence Theory (Ang & Earley, 2003) and (2) the Social Identity Theory (Tajfel, 1978; Tajfel & Turner, 1979) to analyze the interplay between personal development, educational experiences, intercultural competence, and cultural diversity of SEA Teachers to uncover the challenges and strategies (Idrus, 2021; & Tavares, 2021) associated in the Philippine context. Cultural intelligence prepares international students in acculturation to further understand verbal and non-verbal communication regardless of different cultures (Chkhikvadze et al., 2019), whereas social identity impacts teaching innovation behaviors. Thus, teaching performance requires continual advancements to provide innovative and quality learning experiences to students (Cao et al., 2022).

Despite the resulting impact of internationalizing teacher education and highlighting cross-cultural communication, little attention has been given to the matter of how to construct a curriculum that has an introspection on an international dimension and, consequently, how to prepare more globally competent teachers (Panigrahi & Naaz, 2021). Access to education without quality is a waste of time and opportunity. Teachers must be equipped with the necessary skills, knowledge, and experience to improve teacher education globally for the students (Agustin & Montebon, 2018; Byram, 1997; Fantini, 2009). In this program, the teachers must be prepared for the culturally diverse environment they will be immersed in as they work with children, parents, and the school faculty (Romjin et al., 2020). Learning the academic role of culturally diverse environments and cross-cultural communication will be vital in the future as the world slowly pushes toward globalization.

This study aims to identify the role of intercultural competence in the academic world by identifying essential experiences and challenges faced by the SEA Teachers during their internship in the Philippines, providing insights to enhance the international student-teacher exchange programs while creating an inclusive and culturally responsive learning environment.

Research Questions

The researchers of this study seek to explore what SEA teachers feel and experience throughout their time teaching in a foreign country and look into the intercultural factors that affect their performance in educating their students. To be specific, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the challenges and experiences of the SEA teachers in adapting to the Philippines educational system?
2. What is the significance of intercultural awareness in adapting to a foreign school?

Literature Review

The Presence of International Students in Philippine Schools

The state of affairs experienced by international students in Philippine schools is frequently studied (Eridani et al., 2019; Joseph & Wa, 2013; Santillan et al., 2018). However, their presence in the local academe lacks investigation as existing studies might not accurately portray the various situations (Tria, 2020) international students could find themselves in a period after the COVID-19 Pandemic.

International students require an environment that provides a respectable level of quality regarding when it comes to their basic needs to survive life abroad (Bautista et al., 2023). This extends to the material used for learning, where students expect to use it post-exchange program (Olipas et al., 2022). Cultural adaptation plays a significant role in the trials and adjustments that are experienced by international students as they spend their time in a private Philippine university. Coping mechanisms on the difficulties encountered resulted in the length of stay having a negative correlation with cultural empathy and open-mindedness, while a positive correlation was noted on the international students' adaptability with length of stay (Santillan et al., 2018).

However, several factors hinder international students from reaching their full potential in a new environment such as language barrier, lack of good study habits, and lack of motivation (Monteron, 2021). Some international students struggle with the fear of being ostracized should they fail to keep up with the discussions that take place (Sumalinog, 2018). International students tend to utilize the support from the local environment as a coping mechanism (Arde et al., 2020), without proper support from the locals, international students may also feel more stressed when adapting to a new culture (Nimako, 2021).

Overseas Academic Experiences of International Students

Over time, the popularity of international education has grown, and more students are choosing to pursue their academic careers abroad (Global et al. Centre, 2023; & Magkilat, 2022). For international students, the chance to study overseas can be a once-in-a-lifetime experience that exposes them to various cultures, languages, and ways of thinking (Sobkowiak, 2019).

There has been a sudden positive trend of students traveling to countries that are more developed than their homeland for a higher quality education (Findlay et al., 2004), and because of this, researchers have grown interested in identifying the aspects that alter the students' performance in their studies and the events they encounter as they study in a foreign country. The study noted that one of the most significant factors influencing the students' perception towards their learning environment was academic discipline (Junaid et al., 2018). Oftentimes, school systems encompass a student's adherence to rules and regulations while also reflecting their ability to discern right from wrong, which makes academic discipline fundamental for a well-functioning educational institution as it supports academic success and character development (Agak et al., 2016). While studying abroad does not only become significant on the academic aspect, but it holds a significant role in the long run as it provides personal growth, cultural development, advancement in language learning, and social integration (Dwyer, 2004).

Foreign students with varying race or ethnic groups may or may not have differing experiences as they study in a foreign country (Gudykunst, 2017). A group filled with various nationalities may impact a foreign student's learning experience negatively (Laskareva, 2021). A majority of respondents also struggled to learn a new culture. Since these foreign students had to adapt themselves to fit into a foreign country, it would only be natural that this came with adjusting to its cultural norms, academic structure, language, and other societal factors part of the academic and social landscape (Yilmaz & Temizkan, 2020). The foreign students were confronted with the dissimilarities, and the potential issues that could be caused by these. Some of the contrasting elements mentioned were the style of clothing, expressing one's sexuality, food, and the language gap. The potential cultural collisions faced by the students contributed to the experiences of the foreign students (Kusek, 2015).

Moreover, the study's population faced difficulties with speaking and understanding the English language, leading to communication challenges and hindering their ability to express thoughts and feelings effectively. The respondents exhibited varying behaviors when interacting with fluent English speakers and had to be highly self-aware to avoid miscommunication and potentially embarrassing situations (Yilmaz & Temizkan, 2020). Despite the given struggles, the English language has become a necessity for communication and language development since it is considered a universal language (Vyomakesisri, 2017).

Further, there were some disparities in academic challenges, cultural adjustment, and social isolation based on how international students adjust to the educational system. The reason for that was mainly that it was different from their own nation, and their inexperience of how to work within the new system added to the difficulties. The challenges that students have in the classroom can be viewed from the standpoint of cultural capital, a component that must be rebuilt when they enter a new social environment (Garza et al., 2015).

For students to excel in their academic careers, they must rebuild their cultural capital (Jiao et al., 2022). Furthermore, the reasons why international students' attitudes and behavior differ depending on the social situation were also highlighted by variations in attitude and behavior. All participants agreed that their behaviors and attitudes reflected their surroundings and the people they came into contact with, such as their coworkers, family members, and friends. Sometimes, students acted in ways that would help them acclimate or assert their status as international students by using their differences in attitude or behavior (Albarracin & Shavitt, 2018; Yilmaz &

Temizkan, 2020).

Phan et al.'s (2019) study focused on the experiences of foreign students in Singapore regarding the English language. Many of the international students actively attempted to integrate themselves into the foreign environment. The study noted that language barriers influenced the students' performances, in a way that some teachers and students use a local dialect during lectures and class discussions, thus preventing them from communicating efficiently with others.

Some research also focused on the experiences of international students studying abroad. Yoon and Smith (2018) conducted a study about challenges faced by international students while adapting to a new academic and cultural environment. Results showed that international students encounter significant difficulties such as language barriers, differences in academic expectations and teaching styles, and culture shock. Additionally, Choudaha & Kono's (2018) study investigated the role of social media in shaping perceptions and experiences of international students and found that social media can help students connect with their peers and even help them navigate their new environment.

Similarly, Rezaei et al.'s (2018) study revolved around the role of the host country's culture in the academic performance and social integration of students. Results showed that host country culture significantly influences international students' academic performance and significantly impacts students' social integration. Lee and Rice's (2020) study focused on the academic experience of international students in the United States. It concluded that international students face additional challenges in online learning, such as communication barriers and time-zone differences.

International students often face several challenges that can impact their academic and social integration into a new environment and can range from language barriers and cultural differences to teaching styles and expectations. Moreover, the experiences of international students have become increasingly complex with the rapid shift towards online learning environments, which require additional skills and resources. By addressing these challenges and providing the necessary support, international students can have a positive and rewarding experience while studying abroad.

The Emerging Status of Intercultural Awareness in an Academic Setting

Intercultural Awareness has become an essential tool for the successful coexistence of people from various cultural backgrounds. However, not everyone is aware of cultural differences and continues to hold onto ethnocentrism and unfavorable prejudices. As a result, numerous research was conducted to improve people's intercultural awareness (Malović & Vujica, 2021; Soobratty, 2015; Yuldashbayevna, 2020).

Ahmed's (2020) study examined the cultural collisions among foreign students in a university in Turkey. Results show that disputes about intercultural communication mostly arise when the differences between people's backgrounds are ignored because of intolerance and ignorance. Therefore, it was discovered that intercultural conflicts grow when incompatibility exists owing to ignorance of cultural differences, and diminish when people from diverse backgrounds share mutual values and standards. Participants said that after meeting people from various backgrounds, their perspectives altered and evolved throughout time.

The teacher has a vital role in developing a learner's ability to adapt to cultural differences (Salih & Omar, 2021). Enhancing intercultural competence among teachers can be achieved by integrating components from different regions of the country into the curriculum. Through service learning and student reflections, teachers can infuse knowledge of bilingualism and multiculturalism, enabling them to conduct diverse activities and foster a more inclusive educational experience (Baigorri & Crowley, 2011; Calahan et al., 2021; Goldberg, 2007; Ivygena et al., 2019).

Similar to the result of Salih and Omar's (2021) study, Vukić et al. (2019) noted that all the participants value cultural variety and are also eager to learn more about intercultural awareness. The participants joined a course with a limited grasp of IC (Intercultural communication) theoretical ideas and their terms, but were able to offer examples and recognize theoretical appearances in the real world intuitively; However, they lacked an ability to provide certain terms. The participants perceived their knowledge on intercultural communication to be more on the theoretical ground than on practical grounds.

Student-teachers struggle with socialization and communication skills despite being open to others. However, they clearly understood various cultures' worldviews and unanimously agreed that a universal worldview does not exist (Echcharfy, 2022).

The Role of Educators in Fostering Intercultural Competence within Diverse Educational Environments

In the evolving landscape of internationalized education, teachers play a critical role in promoting intercultural understanding (IC) among students. Whereas, IC allows teachers to effectively connect with students from various backgrounds, fostering a welcoming and inclusive learning environment. Research suggests that integrating specific learning objectives about cultural diversity into teacher training programs is crucial. By exposing educators to the realities of multiethnic, multilingual, and multireligious societies, these programs better equip them to manage and leverage the richness of cultural diversity in their classrooms (Vižintin, 2018).

Studies emphasize that developing IC requires self-reflection on personal cultural experiences and biases. This reflection helps teachers reduce ethnocentric tendencies and enhance their cultural sensitivity, leading to more effective interactions and teaching methods in diverse classrooms. For example, research by Winarti (2017) shows that encouraging teacher reflection on cultural differences can

significantly improve learning quality by fostering a deeper understanding of students' cultural backgrounds and educational needs. Furthermore, intercultural training equips teachers to recognize not only visible differences but also the invisible aspects of diversity, such as group-level and individual variations. This refined understanding, as highlighted by Jokikokko (2005), plays a vital role in supporting the academic and personal growth of all students.

Ultimately, fostering IC in educators is no longer optional but essential in today's diverse educational settings. Effective intercultural training equips teachers to navigate the complexities of cultural diversity, ultimately creating a dynamic and inclusive learning environment. This underscores the need for ongoing professional development and targeted educational policies that prioritize building intercultural competence among educators. By ensuring teachers are well-prepared, we empower them to enrich the multicultural landscapes of modern educational institutions (Gravenstijn, 2019).

Methodology

Research Design

This study used qualitative methods to collect and analyze data. In order to understand the intercultural experiences of the participants, the study used a phenomenological design. Purposeful sampling determined the participants of the study, which were international student-teachers under the SEA Teacher Exchange Program Pilot Batch 2, ideally those who are fluent in English.

Data collection was conducted via Focus Group Discussion (FGD) with the use of ten (10) guide questions as instrument. Prior to the interview, the researchers ensured that the participants had understood and signed the consent forms that were given. The participants were also inquired before the use of recording devices should concerns regarding their privacy arise. Data analysis was done with thematic analysis for the ease of data interpretation.

Participants

By using purposeful sampling, the participants of the study are ensured to provide relevant and substantial insights into the phenomenon being studied. Six international student-teachers of legal age (at least 18 years) are involved, specifically two representatives from each country (Japan, Indonesia, and Thailand) since there are limited participants. The respondents are labeled according to their respective nationalities, such as Japanese, Indonesian, and Thai.

Furthermore, the criteria for selection included international student-teachers who were part of the SEA Teacher Exchange Program Pilot Batch 2 and another essential requirement for inclusion was fluency in English, to facilitate effective communication during data collection and to ensure that nuances in experiences were accurately captured and expressed.

Instruments

For two consecutive days of hybrid semi-structured interview via Focus Group Discussion (FGD) of six (6) respondents, the study is guided by a set of 10 open-ended self-constructed guide questions as reviewed and content validated by a professional teacher. The instrument is fractioned in three components: (1) informed consent form and data privacy clause; (2) profile of respondent, including sex, age, years in service of teaching, and nationality; and (3) questions on the role of intercultural competence and awareness when facing challenges in a foreign country and adjusting to its cultural norms.

Procedure

Prior to the collection of data, this research has been approved by the Ethics Review Committee with an approval code of ERC-2023 172. By conducting focus group discussions with six participants from the South East Asian (SEA) Teacher Program in Central Luzon State University, University Science High School (CLSU-USHS), through an audio recorded semi-structured interview, the wide range of topics that can arise given the various nationalities involved was summarized on the research instrument constructed by the researchers. This approach incorporates open-ended discussions about the questions between researchers and respondents. Consequently, coding and thematic analysis was conducted upon analyzing data, making interpretation easier and much more practical.

Ethical Considerations

The study was approved and conducted according to the guidelines of the Central Luzon State University (CLSU) Ethics Research Committee (ERC), with protocol approval code 2023-172.

Results and Discussion

The initial aim of this study was to explore the role of intercultural competence in the academic world by examining the experiences and challenges faced by Southeast Asian (SEA) student teachers during their internships in the Philippines. This investigation intended to provide actionable insights that could enhance international student-teacher exchange programs and foster a more inclusive, culturally responsive educational environment.

Overcoming Challenges

As student-teachers embark on their journey to explore and enrich their capabilities and knowledge, encountering struggles and

challenges are inevitable, especially in a foreign country. Among the notable challenges encountered by these aspiring educators range from English as their second language, the fact that it was their first-time teaching, and struggles in cultural adaptation.

In a world interconnected by the wonders of technology, advancements contrast in countries such as Japan, Indonesia, Thailand, and the Philippines, as the subjects of the study shared some of their experiences in the host country.

“The technology and public transportation are quite different...like you have technological programs like Wi-Fi, and it is so weak, right? Also, like the way we use the restroom, like you know, the equipment, ours is very high-tech in a way. But, you know, it took some time for us to adjust. Once you get used to it, it's just fine,” a Japanese student-teacher discussed the varying levels of technological advancement.

“I find it hard sometimes to take out some money because I'm not so familiar with the ATM machine... I actually tried in the Landbank here but it's not working, so I have to go to Walter Mart in San Jose or the market at the Muñoz. It's actually kind of inconvenient sometimes. Also, for groceries, there's some kind of struggle to buy some, since I cannot go out then come back here really easily, but thanks to the old market, I was really helped that much when I only needed basic groceries,” shared an Indonesian student-teacher who experienced unfamiliarity with local services.

“In the Philippines, people mostly do walk, but in Thailand, I ride a motorcycle. Even when I go to study in university, I ride motorcycle, so it's easy, but here it's kind of tiring, because you're like exercising every time when you go to different buildings, like from the guest house to the school is a little far,” as the Thai student-teacher felt the need to adapt to the local practices and norms.

In the 1950s, the Philippines ranked second to Japan in industrial, technological, and economic development in Asia. However, over time, its neighboring countries in East Asia surpassed its progress. As a developing nation, the Philippines embraced techno liberalism, believing that technology and free-market principles would drive economic and social growth. This led to a heavy reliance on foreign technologies and a decline in investment in local science and technology. As a result, domestic technology remained underdeveloped and unable to meet the needs of local industries, forcing the continued importation of foreign technologies while still falling behind world-class standards (Atanasoski & Vora, 2019; Posadas, 1999; Posadas, 2009).

International students may face challenges in integrating into the local community due to limited access to technology, establishments, transportation, private residences, and university facilities. These restrictions can affect their ability to carry out daily activities, potentially impacting the overall appeal of the location for international students (Adnett, 2010; Kusek, 2015).

However, a Japanese student-teacher discerned that technological differences were not a hindrance for the institution and the locals on leaving a good impression: *“So, yeah, even if some things are quite different. The behavior of people is similar, very modest, very humble, very well-disciplined, that's what we thought...But I feel like this country is still advancing well and the people here have passion, the guts to improve.”*

Despite being technologically outdated, the hospitality of the common Filipino made the experience of the student teacher in the Philippines meaningful. The ability of many Filipinos to speak and understand English, alongside hospitality, are traits applicable to Filipinos that allow foreigners to enjoy the company of the locals (Florida, 2006).

On another note, the challenge of navigating English as a second language emerges as a significant aspect of the student-teachers' journey. While shaping the young minds in foreign lands, the intricacies of language fluency, communication, and cultural nuances weave a compelling narrative as they explore both the obstacles they encounter and the unique perspectives they bring not only to the classroom but also in their lives.

“Philippines treats English as their second language while in Indonesia as foreign but somehow uh, when we speak English, we feel more accepted here in the Philippines,” an Indonesian teacher discussed their experiences with using English as a second language in the Philippines, discussing how Filipinos are more lenient compared to Indonesians.

Frederiksen (2014) stated in their study that while native English speakers have a better capability in using the language in a communicative sense, non-native English speakers like Filipinos have a better understanding of the language's grammar. This could contribute to a better environment for the foreign teachers since the spoken English language is less intimidating, but the speakers are knowledgeable enough that they can learn from them.

“People here...the filipinos' English is so good. And I have trouble communicating some words, may not be spoken the same as you. My pronunciation sometimes causes misunderstanding. I often use a translator on Google to communicate because I can't say the words,” expressed one of the Thai student-teachers in awe and appreciation for the fluency and proficiency of Filipinos in the English language.

In Europe and the USA, numerous international students face challenges in speaking fluently, even after passing language tests. This language inadequacy leaves them feeling disadvantaged and makes social interaction with local students a difficult task (Wright & Yu, 2016). Consequently, these negative experiences during their time of studying may not be well-processed, leading to feelings of loneliness (Brown, 2008). Further, language inadequacy and challenges in social communication led to a sense of non-acceptance, being ignored, and overall dissatisfaction among international students (Ryan & Viète, 2009). International students in the USA

encountered difficulties in social interaction with local students, particularly during their first year, thus, facing challenges in teamwork and sociocultural adaptation (Woods et al., 2020).

Meanwhile, the prospect of teaching for the first time abroad brings forth a multitude of challenges and opportunities, where language barriers, diverse teaching methodologies, and the distinctions of local customs intertwine. International student-teachers begin their initial teaching venture overseas, uncovering the joys, triumphs, and occasional struggles that shape their educational odyssey in a new cultural milieu. The collection of statements below was said by the Indonesian and Japanese student-teachers, saying that it was their first-time teaching in general:

"I don't have any expectations because it's unfair for me because this is my first-time teaching. Actually, not only teaching but also teaching in general..." said an Indonesian student-teacher when asked regarding their expectations towards their foreign students.

"That's all, because teaching is quite new for me here, and especially this is my first-time teaching. I was- I already do that before but it's not quite turned out well," said another Indonesian student-teacher who was not discouraged after encountering trials in the beginning of his teaching career.

"Yeah, for me too. Like um, so this is my first practice teaching in general of course. I have never taught the students in Japan and also the way that teachers teach here, and also in Japan... They are quite different, very different," further explained a Japanese student-teacher.

Even with the lack of experience, it has been noted in previous studies that pre-service teachers use their autobiographical knowledge to motivate their students (Mpfu, 2017). While it is nerve wracking to start out in a foreign country, it can prove to be a worthwhile experience.

Enriching Experiences

Intercultural Competence

Intercultural competence is a crucial aspect of education that enables students and teachers to develop a better understanding of diverse cultures and perspectives. The student-teacher exchange program provided an opportunity for the teachers to enhance their intercultural competence and awareness by interacting with students from a different cultural background. As a result, the teachers became more conscious of cultural differences and they learned to respect and value them. They also developed effective communication skills across cultures, which is crucial in today's globalized world.

Cultural Awareness and Sensitivity

During the student-teacher exchange program, the SEA teachers recognized the diversity of their students and their own cultural biases and values, which could impact their teaching style and interactions with students. They emphasized the need to be aware of and sensitive to different cultural norms and beliefs, such as religion, to create a welcoming and inclusive environment.

A Japanese teacher stated that the biggest difference between the countries is religion: *"So, we...actually, like, it's so common in Japan to not have the religion, like specific that you believe".* He also emphasized the importance of caring for each other despite the cultural differences: *"When it comes to living together, not like meeting as a friend or like that's it. We're living together, we're having like meals together. We need to, you know, care about each other's culture, right? So that's interesting 'cuz we're like, you know, re-rounding the importance of caring about the culture including religion, the perspectives, you know...24/7 lives together."*

Research has shown that cultural sensitivity can have a positive impact on intercultural communication. Participants who had a higher level of cultural sensitivity were better able to accurately interpret the emotions of people from different cultures, leading to more positive interactions (Lee & Fiske, 2016). Similarly, a study by Kashima and Loh (2016) found that cultural sensitivity was positively associated with perceived trust and empathy in intercultural communication.

A Japanese teacher later discussed that having a perspective wherein we treat every culture equally can help us appreciate cultural differences: *"So like, with that awareness, like, even like no one's culture and no one's perspectives is greater than the other, you know? We can accept, like... I could accept the differences between the...the difference is not like a high position and a low position – no. It's equal, it's even."*

According to Kim (2016), cultural awareness is the first step towards developing intercultural competence as it allows individuals to understand and appreciate the differences between cultures. This includes recognizing one's own cultural biases and values, as well as being open to learning about other cultures.

According to Krechetnikov and Mihina (2019), effective intercultural communication (ICC) involves adopting an approach that acknowledges and respects cultural differences, promotes cultural sensitivity, and develops strategies for building meaningful connections with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds.

The SEA teachers also acknowledged the importance of learning about the host country's similarities and differences with their own culture and how to apply it to their teaching methods.

“If you go to certain places, either in your country or abroad, and then learn or teach there, you will get a different perspective like, for example, I get a new way to teach which I’m going to use when I go back to Indonesia. So, that’s the main thing, you will get different perspective, you will get different knowledge, you will get new things that you can actually apply either when you’re going to study or being a teacher- going to teach or doing that at the same time,” added an Indonesian teacher when asked if the student-teacher program is effective and beneficial.

Individuals with a culturally sensitive perspective tend to have better intercultural communication skills and are more likely to be successful in cross-cultural interactions (Gopalkrishnan, 2019). Another study by Collier and Thomas (2016) found that a perspective of cultural relativism can lead to greater tolerance and acceptance of different cultural practices and beliefs.

Interpersonal Skills

The SEA teachers highlighted the need to develop strong interpersonal skills, such as showing respect, and actively listening to the students, to be able to effectively communicate and build relationships with people from different cultures. The teachers also emphasized the need to be open-minded and willing to learn from others in order to develop strong interpersonal skills during the student-teacher exchange program.

An Indonesian Teacher explained that Filipino students are more active and are willing to help them with their grammar whenever they make any mistakes: *“The students sometimes correct us when we make mistakes and then we’re really grateful for that. The students here are really active so...there’s no problem (with communication).”*

The teacher's acknowledgement of the students' helpfulness and activity level shows a recognition and appreciation of the cultural differences between the Indonesian and Filipino students. This demonstrates the importance of intercultural competence in developing strong interpersonal skills in ICC (Intercultural Communication).

Active listening involves receiving messages accurately, attending to nonverbal cues, providing feedback to the speaker, and suspending judgment until the speaker's message is fully understood (Lustig & Koester, 2019). By actively listening to the students and accepting their feedback, the teacher is demonstrating a willingness to suspend judgment and understand their perspective, which can contribute to a more effective and respectful communication. This can, in turn, lead to a positive and collaborative relationship between the teacher and students, and can also help to create a respectful learning environment.

Gudykunst and Kim (2017) explore the concept of intercultural communication and offer strategies for improving communication between people from different cultures. The book emphasizes the importance of cultural awareness, sensitivity, and adaptation in intercultural communication, as well as the impact of cultural differences on communication.

Cross-cultural Education

Socialization among people from different cultures involves the recognition of cultural differences, which may bring impactful and insightful experiences to one's personal and professional life. As a significant aspect of modern education, the improving condition of cross-cultural education enables individuals to understand and appreciate diverse cultural perspectives.

“I think that the students in Indonesia still lack the socialization about how English works right now, especially in the globalization era, because English really helps us to go anywhere. Since I am majoring in English Language Education, I found that English takes me everywhere. When I go to Philippines, I was like struggling like it has a fear before of expecting how do I communicate with someone. But thankfully, I could still use English, and it’s not really hard for others to understand. Although sometimes it’s broken English, but communication is there, unlike in Indonesia, so it’s not hard to adjust,” as one of the Indonesian teachers shared their outlook on their adjustments to the host country while pointing out the utilization of English in a global perspective.

Meanwhile, the other Indonesian teacher mentioned their observations between the host country from their home country: *“In here, we found that people in the Philippines are more disciplined than in Indonesia. But I found here we are really disciplined, especially with time management and also how the working ethics are so...when we start from 7AM, it really starts from 7AM. And for the similarities, it’s basically the same in Indonesia, like the food, but since (participant A) doesn’t eat pork due to religion...but the taste and spiciness taste the same. It really feels like home sometimes.”*

Research shows that it is crucial for teachers to first recognize and comprehend their own worldviews to be effective with diverse students. Educators are the ones to address learner diversity, thus, providing inclusivity to all races, ethnicity, language, religion, and sexual orientation (Milinga & Possi, 2017).

In the present globalized world, diversity provides a platform to build stronger relationships by exposing individuals to different cultures, languages, and perspectives. Cross-cultural education develops an individual's sense of empathy and respect on the different cultural backgrounds (Mansilla & Gardner, 2007).

A Thai teacher emphasized the importance of the program towards globalization through intercultural communication, *“Yes, I think (the program) is very important because we come from different countries, different cultures, and different languages. We need to realize and to learn and understand in order to live here. I learned a lot of things. My habits and cultures, not just in the Philippines,*

but the countries Japan and Indonesia, too – with either something new and good knowledge.”

Effective and competent communication is essential in bridging cultural differences and fostering mutual understanding. It requires an appreciation of how cultures differ fundamentally and how they react differently to similar situations. Whereas, cross-cultural education involves learning about non-verbal communication, cultural norms, and values. Since distinct non-verbal communication styles naturally occur from various cultures, educators must be vigilant when teaching in a diverse classroom (Dreser, 1996; Banks et al., 2001).

“Even though we have different nationalities, I realize that there can be no small differences between each country. Students, or teachers, like finding the similarities, finding the differences. I mean, you can compare, if you don't outside yourself, by joining those kinds of programs, you can't compare it right? So, by exposing yourself, and as a teacher, to another country, you can get another perspective. That's what makes the program special, I guess, like that. You know, not as an international student, but education in general, you know, education is the key...education is the only thing that remains forever,” stated a Japanese teacher on the importance of quality education despite being a foreign teacher.

Education is a continuous learning process for everyone, where teachers also learn since they are in a never-ending process of developing their cultural knowledge and cross-cultural communication skills (Johnson, 2006), which can be fostered in student exchange programs. Global competence is only the beginning for the field of cross-cultural education.

Significance of the Program

With a program that exchanges teachers from foreign countries, there is no doubt that there are significant benefits that come with the experiences. The student-teacher exchange program has provided the teachers the opportunity to experience a classroom setting, as well as teach a class in a laboratory science high school. The teachers were able to express what significance the program has provided.

“I believe that every student-and-teacher program is effective and beneficial either for the student, or the teacher itself because you will get different perspectives,” an Indonesian student-teacher stated their thoughts on the benefits of the student-teacher exchange program.

“It has become a chance for us to broaden our perspectives as teachers, by learning methods different from our countries,” as the Japanese student-teachers agreed. They further said, *“So by exposing yourself, and as a teacher, to another country, you can get another perspective — That's what makes the program special.”*

“I think it's extremely helpful and effective,” claimed the student-teachers from Thailand.

Statements of the teachers correspond to the results of the study of Barr (1995), which claims that all of the individuals had a positive time abroad, but the process had enhanced rather than changed their pre-existing beliefs and philosophies.

One of the Japanese teachers has stated how they wouldn't be able to learn about new teaching methods if they did not participate in the program: *“If I didn't join this program, I couldn't learn teaching methods...I joined this program so I could learn things different from the Japanese way.”*

This statement is relative to the results of Leutwyler's (2014) study, which concluded that student-teachers who took part in an overseas student teaching experience provided proof that teaching specific self-efficacy beliefs are promoted during an international teaching experience. Student-exchange programs should be introduced more to improve developing relations between countries and help student teachers have a broad perspective on the relevance of education (Mphahlele et al., 2017).

The teachers have a variety of insightful favorable viewpoints to share on the advantages of the student-teacher exchange program. According to their statements, these programs offer worthwhile chances for them to extend their cultural experiences and develop perspectives on education. They also emphasized the advantages of these programs for their own professional growth as teachers. The findings indicate that student-teacher exchange programs are highly regarded by educators and regarded as an effective means of fostering cross-cultural understanding and cooperation in the global community.

Conclusion

The SEA teachers' tenure at the Laboratory High School was marked by significant growth through overcoming various challenges and immersing in enriching experiences, which underscores the profound impact of the international student-teacher exchange programs. The array of challenges faced, ranging from technological differences to language barriers, fostered a deep appreciation for cultural diversity and led to substantial professional and personal development among the teachers. These experiences highlight the indispensable role of intercultural competence and cultural awareness, which not only facilitate smoother transitions in such programs but also lower entry barriers, broadening the scope for more teachers to participate and benefit from enhanced social mobility.

Through this program, SEA teachers expanded their educational perspectives, acquiring valuable cross-cultural education strategies that are applicable in their home countries. This engagement has honed their interpersonal skills, such as active listening and respect, crucial for effective communication and relationship building across diverse cultural landscapes. Moreover, the program significantly

contributed to their cultural sensitivity, helping them recognize and navigate cultural biases and values. Such developments have reinforced the significance of the program in creating an inclusive and welcoming environment, promoting an appreciation of diverse cultural perspectives, and enhancing overall intercultural competence.

Hence, the implications of this study suggest that further enriching these programs by continuously integrating comprehensive intercultural training and support can amplify their effectiveness. Enhancing the structure and content of the exchange programs to foster deeper intercultural engagements will not only improve the experiences of future participants but also contribute to the global competency of educators, ultimately benefiting the educational ecosystems both locally and internationally.

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